

Deliverable

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D6.2-Operational public website with logo

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Dissemination Level		
P	Public	x
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	

Abstract:

This document provides information on the project website and the logo created for the project ImAc.

Both the website and the logo have been designed with accessibility principles and both have been tested with end users.

REVISION HISTORY

Revision	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
0.1	05-12-2017	Pilar Orero	UAB	ToC
0.2	15-12-2017	Chris Hughes	USAL	ToC Consolidation
0.3	19-12-2017	Pilar Orero	UAB	Final draft
0.4	14-01-2018	Pilar Orero	UAB	Final revision

Disclaimer

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Statement of originality:

This document contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the end user requirements to make the ImAc accessible in both its web and logo. Given the fact that ImAc deals with media accessibility, it was decided to set up a separate effort from the general Dissemination Plan D6.1. Both the web and the logo were designed to fulfil accessibility requirements and in a way, preach accessibility and user-centric design with good examples. The different sections of the web, and the approach to deal with 360 content are also contained in this Deliverable.

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1. LOGO

1.1. Choices

From a selection of logos to be found below in Figure 1 three sets of logo were developed.

Figure 1 First logos

The logo would represent the visual identity and is the combination of graphics, type and colour. It drives the project advertising and is the visual thread that ties the project objectives together. The visual identity is very much the branding of the project as a whole. For ImAc the choice of logo was not left to the partners, but to some users in the UK and UAB to decide the best choice for accessibility.

Proposal 1

Inspired on curve screens and the new 360 broadcasting platforms. Simple and clear solution to work on big and small sizes.

Figure 2 Logo proposal 2

Proposal 2

In this logo accessibility was seen as something that complements the new immersive technologies that are emerging today. As an additional layer, as a parallel framework that follows the new solutions.

Figure 3 Proposal 2

Proposal 3

This was the logo chosen. It was chosen because of its formative look and feel, bold and simple, clear and catchy, similar concept as proposal 2. Good colours and contrast. From the four possibilities developed see Fig 4. below one was chosen.

Figure 4 Four options of the chosen logo

1.1.1. Colour contrast

The ImAc logo is available in three variations, including a single version for full-white usage when the background is dark. Contrast, font readability and clear composition are designed to fit Accessibility WCAG standards: <https://www.w3.org/WAI/intro/wcag>

Figure 5 Options for chosen logo

The ImAc palette includes 4 primary colours. All colours passed “AA” Colour Accessibility Standards and was check at <http://www.contrastchecker.com>

Figure 6 Colours chosen for ImAc

1.1.2. Typography

The ImAc webpage works with Muli Google Font (<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Muli>). This font offers great readability in small sizes. It is a sans serif, helping to read on screen, and since ImAc is also designed for other devices this font was considered to suit best all devices.

Figure 7 Muli Google Font

1.1.3. Tests

The logos were presented to two end users in Catalonia and three in UK. While all logos were accessible the final choice was

Figure 8 The chosen logo

Because it had two colours, and made it more interesting.

2. WEBSITE

The website was also designed at UAB with accessibility requisites. The website is already functional <http://www.imac-project.eu>. The web can be consulted on multiple screens with the same quality.

Figure 9 ImAc in different screens

The website has been created in Karen WordPress Theme ensuring “AA” accessibility standards. Since its conception the categories and sections were to be considered functional

and informative, and aims at evolving with the project content, a showcase of its developments.

Figure 10 Karen Theme

The website was generated by UAB with the technical support of IRNB and also for usability tests. The website has been sent to partners for comments and feedback before its publication.

2.2. Website screen maps

Major pages are all only one click away from Home Page. This architecture helps to bring clear navigations user flows.

Figure 11 Screen map

2.3. Sections

The web is divided in seven sections. This choice was from:

- the needs and requisites of the project
- experience in previously financed EC projects and
- using the web for raising awareness on accessibility

2.3.1. Home

This is the first image of the web and we decided to add for the time being a 360° picture, and we chose to show the members of the project on the KOM.

Figure 12 Home page

2.3.2. Project

This section has been created with two subsections.

2.3.2.1. Pilots

For the time being a short text has been included to reflect what will be done. As we don't have yet any content, we have decided to re-use existing content produce for a previous project HBB4ALL to promote the accessibility services that will be delivered in 360°:

<http://imac-project.eu/www.imac-project.eu/accessibility-services/>

2.3.2.2. Technical motivation

For the time being we shall use in this section the charts generated for the project proposal. It is expected to have a movie soon explaining the technical motivation.

2.3.3. Immersive Corner

In this section we'll be able to offer examples of the different content created, and it will be used to follow the project evolution. At present we have included visual content in 360 generated by one of the partners CCMA <http://www.ccma.cat/tv3/polonia/polonia-en-360/fitxa/113000/> and also sound generated by another partner IRT <https://lab.irt.de/object-based-radio-drama/>

2.3.4. Documentation

This is the backbone of the web, where all documents are kept together, organised now in 4 subsections, though there may be changes.

2.3.4.1. Publications

Will host all the publications from the project with the wording:

ImAc is committed to share its knowledge with society. For this we make public all our deliverables, research outcome and publications. In this section, you can find the articles and research papers.

Title	Authors	Publication Year	DOI	Permanent Identifier	Publication type	Access Mode
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In the meantime, we have decided to fill in this section with the following. *“Until we have some publications derived from the ImAc project we have decided to fill in this section with the bibliographical references we are using as a basis for our tests in the project organised by sections”* and then we have added a bibliographical list we are using at present.

2.3.4.2. Deliverables

All deliverables will be hosted here

2.3.4.3. Dissemination materials

The dissemination materials will be hosted here

2.3.4.4. Datasets

It is early days and we are not sure if this section will be here under this name or will be move and merge with a different section.

2.3.5. Consortium

The description of all partners is in this section

2.3.6. Contact

This is an interesting page, because added to the contacting information of the project leader i2CAT we have implemented a decision made in the Concentration Day organised by the Unit last October in Brussels.

In order to raise awareness on accessibility, and given the fact that 3 H2020 ICT 19 projects have been awarded in this call, we shall have joint dissemination strategies. One is to add in the URL of the 3 projects information of the other 2 projects. In ImAc we have added this info in this section as can be seen in the image below.

Also in this page, we have the information regarding the Common Dissemination Booster email to contact ImAc cdb02-imag@cdbservices.eu

[Home](#) → [Contact](#)

Contact

For general inquiries, please contact: Sergi Fernandez (project coordinator)

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Other related H2020 funded projects:

CONTENT4ALL

Grant agreement no. 762021

Grant agreement no. 761999

ImAc Project: Immersive Accessibility © ImAc will deliver novel resources for the broadcasting industry to provide adapted content ensuring accessibility in immersive environments

Figure 13 Contact content

2.3.7. News

News regarding the project or interesting news related to 360° or accessibility, the two keywords in the project. News is linked to the centre of HOME, so when you log in the project you are already offered the possibility of reading the latest news.

In D6.1 the policy of publishing a News Story every 2 weeks is explained.

While it was considered to use this section to disseminate any news related to VR or accessibility, this was dismissed, since it may take the form and function of a commercial outlet, and then ImAc news would be diluted in the sea of other news. For this reason, only news related to ImAc will be published, and if there is an important issue related to virtual reality and accessibility, as the news published on the BBC this will be added.

2.4. Web management

UAB has a dedicated person Jara Duro to be the webmaster. She also produces short accessible videos to illustrate activities, such as doing the Ethical Considerations before a Focus Group to be found here: <http://www.imac-project.eu/immersive-corner/tutorials/>

2.5. Social media in the web

While Social Media could be expected to figure at a higher level of interest, it was agreed during the KOM to have only two social media services: Youtube, and Tweet.

The reason to avoid Face Book for example is the high effort required for a very low return. In other EC projects, for example ACT

<https://www.facebook.com/actproject4culture/> at least one item is uploaded daily, the maximum views in three years has been 193 visits for one item, the average is 10 visits. The consortium decided that FaceBook does not cater for research projects. For the same reason LinkedIn was avoided and the consortium decided to focus on two: Youtube and Tweet.

2.5.1. YouTube

The project has to deliver a short movie in D6.4, and that will be delivered and published in Youtube by M16. It is expected to be done then when we have content produced by ImAc. From experience in previous projects we have decided to generate as many as possible very short movies, illustrating the project activities.

An example is the movie generated when doing the first focus group at UAB with blind end users. Given the importance of the Ethical Considerations for ImAc with its own deliverable D.1.2 and the set of documentation created to this aim, it was decided to generate a video to raise awareness of the many steps required when setting up a Focus Group. The video with subtitles can be found here:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0BxrhAOmV4c>

The choice of generating a YouTube channel is also because they offer the possibility of displaying 360º videos, and we plan to have soon some content in that format.

2.5.2. Twitter

Though Twitter was chosen as one of the two social media outlets, not very many followers can be counted, and that is beyond the members of the project effort. This is perhaps an issue to be critical about. Nevertheless there is a dedicated person Belén Agulló from UAB in charge of this service.

The Twitter logo is present in the top right section of the ImAc web.

<END OF DOCUMENT>